

Modeling of toxicity of heterogeneous set of compounds using sterimol and structural parameters[†]

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Abstract : The paper describes modeling of toxicity of a large set of 163 compounds using sterimol and structural parameters. The results indicated that excellent model is obtained using sterimol parameters (π , R and F). The results are discussed using variety of statistical parameters.

Keywords : QSAR, sterimol parameter, structural parameter, toxicity, regression analysis.

Introduction

In the present study we discuss the modeling of toxicity of a larger set of 163 compounds. An investigation made earlier¹⁻³ in modeling of toxicity of compounds has indicated that the methods of testing and modeling of toxicity of organic compounds acting as drugs are changing rapidly. The IGC₅₀ (mg/L) and the 95% fiducially intervals are now used for modeling the toxicity. The IGC₅₀ is calculated by probity analysis using the percent control normalized absorbance as the dependent variable and the toxicant concentration in mg/L as the independent variable. Both the slope and interest of the probity regression equation are recorded as well as other statistical parameters are used for obtaining an appropriate model.

Structure-toxicity modeling⁴ works well in biological activity and modeling. Generally aquatic toxicity and selected human health end points are considered in developing structure-toxicity-relationship. The modeling of relationships between acute and chronic end points is also being examined. Human health end points of particular interest include skin and respiratory sensitization and mammalian inhalation toxicity.

The premise of structure-toxicity-modeling is that changes in the structure of an organic compounds acting

as drug may influence the type and potency of its toxic action. This principle is a continuation of the concept that all chemical toxicological effects are the result of an interaction between the chemical and one or more components of the living systems. These interactions may be reversible or covalent in character. Components of living systems that is capable of reversible or covalent binding with chemicals are related to the molecular sites of action.

The objective of structure-toxicity (QSTR) modeling is two-fold. First we seek to determine as accurately as possible the limits of variation in the structure of a chemical that are consistent with the production of a specific biological effect i.e. toxicity. Secondly, we want to define the ways in which alteration in structure and thereby the overall properties of a compound influence potency. If enough data relates to a specific biological effect (toxicity in the present case) becomes available, a hypothesis can be developed regarding the molecular basis of interaction between the toxicant and its active site.

The development of a structure-toxicity (QSTR) model requires the following three components :

(1) A data set is required that provides toxicity for a group of chemicals. This group is defined particularly by some selection criteria;

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

Table 1 Structural details of compounds used in present study

 Isopropyl benzene			
 3 amino benzyl alcohol			
 4-ethylaniline			
 2-methylaniline			
 2,6-diethylaniline			
 2,3,5-trimethylphenol			
 anisole			
 4-propylphenol			
 2-ethylphenol			
 2-tolunitrile			

Table 1 (contd)

 4-chloro-3,5-dimethylphenol			
 4-chloro-3-methylphenol			
 4-iodophenol			
 1,2-dimethyl-4-nitrobenzene			
 3-chlorophenol			
 benzaldehyde			
 nitrobenzene			
 3,5-dichloroaniline			
 3-chloro-5-methoxyphenol			
 4-chlorobenzaldehyde			
 2,4,6-trichlorophenol			

Table-1 (contd.)

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 2. Sterimol and structural parameters, observed activities of compounds used in present study

No.	Name of compounds	log (IGC ₅₀ ⁻¹)	MR	π	R	L	F	B ₁	B ₅	SD
1	<i>p</i> -Xylene	0.25	11.3	1.12	-0.26	5.74	-0.08	3.04	4.08	1.614
2	Toluene	0.25	5.65	0.56	-0.13	2.87	-0.04	1.52	2.04	0.807
3	<i>n</i> -Butylbenzene	1.25	1.96	2.13	-0.15	6.17	-0.01	1.52	4.54	0
4	Isopropylbenzene	0.69	14.96	1.53	-0.1	4.11	-0.05	1.9	3.17	0.97
5	Benzyl alcohol	-0.83	7.19	-1.03	0	3.97	0	1.52	2.7	1.549
6	4-Ethylbenzyl alcohol	-0.07	17.49	-0.01	-0.1	8.08	-0.05	3.04	5.87	2.472
7	3,4-Dimethylaniline	-0.16	16.72	-0.11	-0.94	8.52	-0.06	4.39	6.05	2.842
8	3-Aminobenzyl alcohol	-1.13	12.61	-2.26	-0.68	6.75	0.02	2.87	4.67	2.777
9	4-Methylaniline	-0.05	11.07	-0.67	-0.81	5.65	-0.02	2.87	4.01	2.035
10	4-Isopropylaniline	0.22	20.38	0.3	-0.78	6.89	-0.03	3.25	5.14	2.198
11	3-Ethylaniline	-0.03	15.72	-0.21	-0.78	6.89	-0.03	2.87	5.14	2.151
12	4-Ethylaniline	0.03	15.72	-0.21	-0.78	6.89	-0.03	2.87	5.14	2.151
13	3-Methylaniline	-0.28	11.07	-0.67	-0.81	5.65	-0.02	2.87	4.01	2.035
14	4-Butylaniline	1.07	7.38	0.9	-0.83	8.95	0.01	2.87	6.51	5.917
15	(2-Bromoethyl)benzene	0.42	19.81	1.88	-0.97	7.93	0.39	3.47	5.12	5.917
16	2-Methylaniline	-0.16	11.07	-0.67	-0.81	5.65	-0.02	2.87	4.01	2.035
17	2,6-Diisopropylaniline	0.76	35.34	1.83	0.68	11	-0.08	5.15	8.31	3.168
18	Aniline	-0.23	5.42	-1.23	-0.68	2.78	0.02	1.35	1.97	1.228
19	2-Ethylaniline	-0.22	15.72	-0.21	-0.78	6.89	-0.03	2.87	5.14	2.151
20	2,6-Diethylaniline	0.31	26.02	0.8	-0.88	11	-0.08	4.39	8.31	3.074
21	4-Methoxyphenol	-0.14	10.72	-0.69	-1.15	6.72	0.55	2.7	5.04	2.27
22	3,4,5-Trimethylphenol	0.93	19.8	1.01	-1.03	11.35	0.17	5.91	8.05	4.691
23	4-Methylanisole	0.25	13.52	0.54	-0.64	6.85	0.22	2.87	5.11	0.807
24	2,3,5-Trimethylphenol	0.36	19.8	1.01	-1.03	11.35	0.17	5.91	8.05	4.691
25	2,4,6-Trimethylphenol	0.42	19.8	1.01	-1.03	11.35	0.17	5.91	8.05	4.691
26	4-(Tert)butylphenol	0.91	4.81	1.46	-0.79	8.91	0.28	2.87	6.47	2.207
27	2,3,6-Trimethylphenol	0.28	19.8	1.01	-1.03	11.35	0.17	5.91	8.05	4.691
28	Anisole	-0.10	7.87	-0.02	-0.51	3.98	0.26	1.35	3.07	0
29	2,4-Dimethylphenol	0.14	14.15	0.45	-0.9	8.48	0.21	4.39	6.01	3.884
30	<i>p</i> -Cresol (4-methylphenol)	-0.16	8.5	-0.11	-0.77	5.61	0.25	2.87	3.97	3.077
31	4-Ethylphenol	0.21	13.15	0.35	-0.74	6.85	0.24	2.87	5.1	3.193
32	4-Propylphenol	0.64	17.81	0.88	-0.72	7.66	0.23	2.87	5.42	2.27
33	3-Ethylphenol	0.29	13.15	0.35	-0.74	6.85	0.24	2.87	5.1	3.193
34	<i>m</i> -Cresol (3-methylphenol)	-0.08	8.5	-0.11	-0.77	5.61	0.25	2.87	3.97	3.077
35	<i>o</i> -Cresol (2-methylphenol)	-0.29	8.5	-0.11	-0.77	5.61	0.25	2.87	3.97	3.077
36	2-Ethylphenol	0.16	13.5	0.35	-0.74	6.85	0.24	2.87	5.1	3.193
37	Phenol	-0.35	2.85	-0.67	-0.64	2.74	0.29	1.35	1.93	2.27
38	Iodobenzene	0.36	13.94	1.12	-0.24	4.23	0.4	2.15	2.55	6.171
39	4-Chloroaniline	0.05	11.45	-0.52	-0.83	6.3	0.43	3.15	3.77	3.892
40	2-Tolunitrile	-0.24	11.98	-0.01	0.06	7.1	0.47	3.12	3.64	4.396
41	2-Chloro-4-methylaniline	0.18	17.1	0.04	-0.96	9.17	0.39	4.67	5.81	4.699
42	2-Chloroaniline	-0.17	11.45	-0.52	-0.83	6.3	0.43	3.15	3.77	3.892
43	3-Methoxyphenol	-0.33	10.72	-0.69	-1.15	6.72	0.55	2.7	5	2.27
44	4-Chloro-3,5-dimethylphenol	1.20	20.18	1.16	-1.05	12	0.62	6.19	7.81	6.548
45	4-Bromotoluene	0.47	14.53	1.42	-0.3	6.69	0.4	3.47	3.99	5.801

46	1-Bromo-4-ethylbenzene	0.67	19.18	1.88	-0.27	7.93	0.39	3.47	5.12	5.917
47	4-Chloroanisole	0.60	13.9	0.69	-0.66	7.5	0.67	3.15	4.87	2.664
48	4-Chloro-3-methylphenol	0.80	14.53	0.6	-0.22	9.13	0.66	4.67	5.77	5.741
49	1,3-Dihydroxybenzene	-0.65	5.7	-1.34	-1.28	5.48	0.58	2.7	3.86	4.54
50	Bromobenzene	0.08	8.8	0.86	-0.17	3.82	0.44	1.95	1.95	4.994
51	4-Chlorophenol	0.54	8.88	0.04	-0.79	6.26	0.7	3.15	3.73	4.934
52	4-Iodophenol	0.85	16.79	0.45	-0.88	6.97	0.69	3.5	4.48	8.441
53	2,4-Dichloroaniline	0.56	17.48	0.19	-0.98	9.82	0.84	4.95	5.57	6.556
54	Chlorobenzene	-0.13	6.03	0.71	-0.15	3.52	0.41	1.8	1.8	2.664
55	3-Chloroaniline	0.22	11.45	-0.52	-0.83	6.3	0.43	3.15	3.77	3.892
56	1,2-Dimethyl-4-nitrobenzene	0.59	18.66	0.84	-0.1	9.18	0.59	4.74	6.52	4.062
57	4-Nitrotoluene	0.65	13.01	0.28	0.03	6.31	0.63	3.22	4.48	3.255
58	4-Isopropylbenzaldehyde	0.67	21.84	0.88	0.03	7.64	0.26	3.5	5.53	2.477
59	1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene	0.56	18.66	0.86	-0.1	9.18	0.59	4.74	6.52	4.062
60	3-Chlorophenol	0.87	8.88	0.04	-0.79	6.26	0.7	3.15	3.73	4.934
61	3-Nitrotoluene	0.42	13.01	0.28	0.03	6.31	0.63	3.22	4.48	3.255
62	2-Nitrotoluene	0.26	13.01	0.28	0.03	6.31	0.63	3.22	4.48	3.255
63	1,4-Dibromobenzene	0.68	17.76	1.72	-0.34	7.64	0.88	3.9	3.9	9.988
64	Benzaldehyde	-0.20	6.88	-0.65	0.13	3.53	0.31	1.6	2.36	1.507
65	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde	-0.03	17.6	-1.34	-1.02	10.25	0.86	4.3	7.36	3.777
66	2,4-Dichlorophenol	1.04	14.91	0.75	-0.94	9.78	1.11	4.95	5.53	7.598
67	2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	0.42	9.73	-1.32	-0.51	6.27	0.6	2.95	4.29	3.777
68	Nitrobenzene	0.14	7.36	-0.28	0.16	3.44	0.67	1.7	2.44	2.448
69	2,5-Dichloroaniline	0.58	17.48	0.19	-0.98	9.82	0.84	4.95	5.57	6.556
70	3,4-Dichlorotoluene	1.07	17.71	1.98	-0.43	9.91	0.78	5.12	5.64	6.135
71	3-Nitroaniline	0.03	12.78	-1.51	-0.52	6.22	0.69	3.05	4.41	3.676
72	3,5-Dichloroaniline	0.71	17.48	0.19	-0.98	9.82	0.84	4.95	5.57	6.556
73	4-Bromo-6-chloro- <i>o</i> -cresol	1.28	20.56	2.13	-0.45	10.21	0.81	5.27	5.79	8.465
74	1,2-Dichlorobenzene	0.53	12.06	1.42	-0.3	7.04	0.82	3.6	3.6	5.328
75	3-Nitroanisole	0.72	15.23	-0.3	-0.35	7.42	0.93	3.05	5.51	2.448
76	3-Chloro-5-methoxyphenol	0.76	16.75	0.02	-1.3	10.24	0.96	4.5	6.8	4.934
77	2,4-Dibromophenol	1.40	20.61	1.05	-0.98	6.56	0.73	3.3	3.88	12.258
78	2-Amino-5-chlorobenzonitrile	0.44	17.78	-1.09	-0.64	10.53	0.94	4.75	5.37	7.481
79	3,5-Dichlorophenol	1.56	14.91	0.75	-0.94	9.78	1.11	4.95	5.53	7.598
80	4-Chlorobenzaldehyde	0.40	12.91	0.06	-0.02	7.05	0.72	3.4	4.16	4.171
81	1,3,5-Trichlorobenzene	0.87	18.09	2.13	-0.45	10.56	1.23	5.4	5.4	7.992
82	2,4,5-Trichloroaniline	1.30	23.51	0.9	-1.13	13.34	1.25	6.75	7.37	9.22
83	1,3,5-Trichlorobenzene	1.08	18.09	2.13	-0.45	10.56	1.23	5.4	5.4	7.992
84	2,4,6-Trichlorophenol	1.41	20.94	1.46	-1.09	13.3	1.52	6.75	7.33	10.262
85	4-Chloro-2-nitrotoluene	0.82	19.04	0.99	-0.12	9.83	1.04	5.02	6.28	5.919
86	1-Bromo-3-nitrobenzene	1.03	16.24	0.58	-0.01	7.26	1.11	3.65	4.39	7.422
87	4-Bromo-2,6-dichlorophenol	1.78	23.79	1.61	-1.11	13.6	1.55	6.9	7.48	12.592
88	2-Chloro-6-nitrotoluene	0.68	19.04	0.99	-0.12	9.83	1.04	5.02	6.28	5.919
89	2,3,5,6-Tetrachloroaniline	1.76	29.54	1.61	-1.28	16.86	1.66	8.55	9.17	11.884
90	3-Nitrobenzotrile	0.45	13.69	-0.85	0.35	7.67	1.18	3.3	4.04	6.037
91	2,4,5-Trichlorophenol	2.10	20.94	1.46	-1.09	13.3	1.52	6.75	7.33	10.262
92	1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene	2.00	24.12	2.84	-0.6	14.08	1.64	7.2	7.2	10.656

<i>Table-2 (contd.)</i>										
93	4-Methyl-2-nitroaniline	0.37	18.43	-0.95	-0.65	9	0.65	4.57	6.45	4.483
94	1-Chloro-3-nitrobenzene	0.73	13.39	0.43	0.01	6.96	1.08	3.5	4.24	5.112
95	2-Nitroaniline	0.08	12.78	-1.51	-0.52	6.22	0.69	3.05	4.41	3.676
96	2,3,4,5-Tetrachloroaniline	1.96	29.54	1.61	-1.28	16.64	1.66	8.55	9.37	11.884
97	2,4,6-Tribromophenol	1.91	29.49	1.91	-1.15	10.38	1.17	5.25	5.83	17.252
98	2-Bromo-5-nitrotoluene	1.16	21.89	1.14	-0.14	10.13	1.07	5.17	6.43	8.249
99	1-Fluoro-3-iodo-5-nitrobenzene	1.09	22.22	0.98	-0.42	10.32	1.5	5.2	6.34	11.605
100	2-Nitrophenol	0.67	10.21	-0.95	-0.48	6.18	0.96	3.05	4.37	4.718
101	2-Chloro-4-nitroaniline	0.75	18.81	-0.8	-0.67	9.74	1.1	4.85	6.21	6.34
102	5-Hydroxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde	0.33	17.09	-1.6	-0.35	9.71	1.27	4.65	6.73	6.225
103	3,4,5,6-Tetrabromo- <i>o</i> -cresol	2.57	44.02	3.33	-1.45	20.89	2.01	10.67	11.77	23.053
104	2,3,4,6-Tetrachlorophenol	2.18	26.96	2.17	-1.24	16.82	1.93	8.55	9.13	12.926
105	1-Fluoro-4-nitrobenzene	0.10	8.28	-0.14	-0.18	6.09	1.1	3.05	3.79	5.434
106	Pentafluoroaniline	0.26	10.02	-0.53	-2.38	16.03	2.17	8.1	8.72	16.158
107	1-Bromo-2-nitrobenzene	0.75	16.24	0.58	-0.01	7.26	1.11	3.65	4.39	7.442
108	3,5-Dibromosalicylaldehyde	1.65	27.49	0.4	-0.85	13.91	1.48	6.85	8.19	13.765
109	3,5-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.13	19.49	1.14	-0.14	10.48	1.49	5.5	6.04	7.776
110	4-Chloro-3-nitrophenol	1.27	16.24	-0.24	-0.63	9.7	1.37	4.85	6.17	7.382
111	2,3,4,5-Tetrachlorophenol	2.72	26.97	2.17	-1.24	16.82	1.93	8.55	9.13	12.926
112	1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene	0.43	13.39	0.43	0.01	6.96	1.08	3.5	4.28	5.112
113	α,α,α -4-Tetrafluoro- <i>m</i> -toluidine	0.77	14.75	-0.11	-2.17	16.25	1.7	8.27	9.41	13.979
114	1-Chloro-2-nitrobenzene	0.68	13.39	0.43	0.01	6.96	1.08	3.5	4.28	5.112
115	4-Chloro-6-nitro- <i>m</i> -cresol	1.63	21.89	0.32	-0.76	12.57	1.33	6.37	8.21	8.189
116	Pentachlorophenol	2.07	33	2.88	-1.39	20.37	2.34	10.35	10.93	15.59
117	1,3-Dinitrobenzene	0.76	14.72	-0.56	0.32	6.88	1.34	3.4	4.88	4.896
118	2,4-Dinitrotoluene	0.87	20.37	0	0.19	9.75	1.3	4.92	6.92	5.703
119	4,5-Dichloro-2-nitroaniline	1.66	24.84	-0.09	-0.82	13.26	1.51	6.65	8.01	9.004
120	Pentafluorophenol	1.63	7.48	0.03	-2.34	15.99	2.44	8.1	8.68	17.2
121	Pentabromophenol	2.66	47.25	3.63	-1.49	21.84	2.49	11.1	11.68	27.24
122	3-Chloro-4-fluoronitrobenzene	0.80	14.31	0.57	-0.33	9.61	1.51	4.85	5.63	8.098
123	1,4-Dinitrobenzene	1.30	14.72	-0.56	0.32	6.88	1.34	3.4	4.88	4.896
124	3,4-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.16	19.42	1.14	-0.14	10.48	1.49	5.3	6.04	7.776
125	2,5-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.13	19.42	1.14	-0.14	10.48	1.49	5.3	6.04	7.776
126	2,4-Dichloro-6-nitroaniline	1.26	24.84	-0.09	-0.82	13.26	1.51	6.65	8.01	9.004
127	3,4-Dinitrobenzyl alcohol	1.09	21.91	-1.59	0.32	10.85	1.34	4.92	7.58	6.445
128	2,4-Dichloronitrobenzene	0.99	19.42	1.14	-0.14	10.48	1.49	5.3	6.04	7.776
129	2,3-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.07	19.42	1.14	-0.14	10.48	1.49	5.3	6.04	7.776
130	1,2-Dinitrobenzene	1.25	14.72	-0.56	0.32	6.88	1.34	3.4	4.88	4.896
131	Phenyl isothiocyanate	1.41	17.24	1.15	-0.09	4.29	0.51	1.5	4.24	0
132	3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol	1.65	18.62	0.03	-1.63	17	2.21	8.62	10.46	14.483
133	2,6-Iodo-4-nitrophenol	1.81	38.09	1.29	-0.96	14.64	1.76	7.35	9.47	17.06
134	2,4-Dichloro-6-nitrophenol	1.75	22.27	0.47	-0.78	13.22	1.78	6.65	7.97	10.046
135	1,3,5-Trichloro-2-nitrobenzene	1.43	25.45	1.85	-0.29	14	1.9	7.1	7.84	10.44
136	1,2,4-Trichloro-5-nitrobenzene	1.53	25.45	1.85	-0.29	14	1.9	7.1	7.84	10.44
137	1,3,3-Trichloro-4-nitrobenzene	1.51	25.45	1.85	-0.29	14	1.9	7.1	7.84	10.44
138	2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzaldehyde	0.53	20.27	-0.22	0.14	10.49	1.39	5.1	6.64	6.619
139	Pentafluorobenzaldehyde	0.82	11.48	0.05	-1.57	16.78	2.46	8.35	9.11	16.473

Table 2 (contd.)

140	2,4-Dinitro-1-iodobenzene	2.12	28.66	-0.44	0.08	11.11	1.74	5.55	7.43	11.067
141	2,3,5,6-Tetrachloronitrobenzene	1.82	31.48	2.56	-0.44	17.52	2.31	8.9	9.64	13.104
142	2,5-Dinitrophenol	1.04	17.57	-1.23	-0.32	9.62	1.63	4.75	6.81	7.166
143	2,4-Dinitroaniline	0.72	20.14	-1.79	-0.32	9.66	1.36	4.75	6.85	6.124
144	2,3,4,5-Tetrachloronitrobenzene	1.78	31.48	2.56	-0.44	17.52	2.31	8.9	9.64	13.104
145	1,2,3-Trifluoro-4-nitrobenzene	1.89	10.12	0.14	-0.86	11.39	1.96	5.75	6.49	11.406
146	1,2-Dichloro-4,5-dinitrobenzene	2.21	26.78	0.86	0.02	13.92	2.16	7	8.48	10.224
147	2,6-Dinitroaniline	0.84	20.14	-1.79	-0.36	9.66	1.36	4.75	6.85	6.124
148	4,6-Dinitro-2-methylphenol	1.73	23.22	-0.67	-0.45	12.49	1.59	6.27	8.85	7.973
149	4-(Tert)butyl-2,6-dinitrophenol	1.80	19.53	0.9	0.47	15.79	1.62	6.27	11.35	7.166
150	1-Bromo-2,4-dinitrobenzene	2.31	23.6	0.3	0.15	10.7	1.78	5.35	6.83	9.89
151	2,4-Dinitrophenol (non-neutralized)	1.06	17.57	-1.23	-0.32	9.62	1.63	4.75	6.81	7.166
152	1,5-Dichloro-2,3-dinitroaniline	2.42	26.78	0.86	0.02	13.92	2.16	7	8.48	10.224
153	6-Chloro-2,4-dinitroaniline	1.12	26.17	-1.08	-0.51	13.18	1.77	6.55	8.65	8.788
154	2-Bromo-4,6-dinitroaniline	1.24	29.02	-0.93	-0.53	13.48	1.8	6.7	8.8	11.122
155	2,3,4,6-Tetrafluoronitrobenzene	1.87	11.04	0.28	-1.2	14.04	2.39	7.1	7.84	14.392
156	2,6-Dinitrophenol	0.83	17.57	-1.23	-0.32	9.62	1.63	4.75	6.81	7.166
157	1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene	2.16	20.75	0.15	0.17	10.4	1.75	5.2	6.68	7.56
158	2,4-Dinitro-1-fluorobenzene	1.71	15.64	-0.42	-0.02	9.53	1.77	4.75	6.23	7.882
159	Pentafluoronitrobenzene	2.43	11.96	0.42	-1.54	16.69	2.82	8.45	9.19	17.378
160	1,4-Dinitrotetrachlorobenzene	2.82	38.84	2.28	-0.28	20.96	2.98	10.6	12.08	15.552
161	1,5-Difluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene	2.08	16.56	-0.28	-0.36	12.18	2.2	6.1	7.58	10.868
162	1,3-Dinitro-2,4,5-trichlorobenzene	2.60	32.81	1.57	-0.13	17.44	2.57	8.8	10.28	12.888
163	4-Chloro-3,5-dinitrobenzotrile	2.66	27.08	-0.42	0.36	14.63	2.26	6.8	8.28	11.149

(2) It is also required that this group of chemicals are property data, and

(3) These two data must be related usually via a statistical analysis method

With this much information regarding modeling of toxicity we now discuss the modeling of toxicities of the larger set of compounds used in the present study (Tables 1 and 2). The results are discussed respectively as below

Results and discussion

The structures of these 163 compounds are presented in Table 1. The toxicity expressed as $\log IGC_{50}$ with sterimol⁵ and structural parameters⁶ are given in Table 2. The selected variables for multiple regression analysis are presented in Table 3. The possible regression models

Table 3. Modeling of activity $\log IGC_{50}$

Model	Parameters used	SE	R ²	R ² _A	F
1	F	0.4728	0.6519	0.6498	301.611
2	π , F	0.3844	0.7713	0.7684	269.881
3	MR, π , F	0.3668	0.7932	0.7893	203.295
4	MR, π , F, B ₁ , B ₅	0.3457	0.8185	0.8127	141.642

for modeling toxicity of these 163 chemicals are given in Table 4. From these data we have to choose the most appropriate model for modeling the toxicities.

The application of rule of thumb⁷ indicates that we can use as many as $163/5 \approx 52$ descriptors for modeling the toxicity of 163 compounds. However, a close look of the referred tables (Table 4) indicates that the maximum number of descriptors used could be seven. The data presented in Table 4 indicates that both R² and R²_A go on increasing with the successive additions of correlating parameters. This happens up to the addition of six correlating parameters. Further addition of correlating descriptors results in decrease in R²_A. Also, we observed that the 6-variable model has R² = 0.8185. However, the 5-parametric model also has R² = 0.8185. In statistics the model having smaller number of correlating parameters is considered better for modeling the activity. It means that the 5-variable is the most appropriate model for modeling toxicity ($\log IGC_{50}$) of the set of 163 compounds. This 5-parametric model is arrived through the following one- to four-variable modeling

Table 4. Details of 5-variable modeling of (log IGC₅₀) activity

Regression statistics							
Multiple R	0.9047						
R square	0.8185						
Adjusted R square	0.8127						
Standard error	0.3457						
Observations	163						
ANOVA							
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F		
Regression	5	84.67749967	16.9355	141.6428	2.60E-56		
Residual	157	18.77167579	0.119565				
Total	162	103.4491755					
	Coefficients	SE	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	
Intercept	-0.37578246	0.088610332	-4.24084	3.79E-05	-0.550805	-0.20076	
MR	0.019234171	0.006112299	3.146798	0.001975	0.0071612	0.031307	
π	0.262174584	0.031794684	8.245862	6.16E-14	0.1993741	0.324975	
F	0.868766601	0.070346038	12.3499	6.51E-25	0.7298199	1.007713	
B ₁	-0.22283190	0.049417227	-4.50919	1.27E-05	-0.32044	-0.12522	
B ₅	0.159447544	0.03712469	4.294919	3.05E-05	0.0861193	0.232776	
RESIDUAL OUTPUT							
Obs.	Obs. log (IGC ₅₀ ⁻¹)	Pre. log (IGC ₅₀ ⁻¹)	Residuals	27	0.28	0.38	-0.10
1	0.25	0.03	0.22	28	-0.10	0.18	-0.28
2	0.25	-0.16	0.41	29	0.14	0.17	-0.03
3	1.25	0.59	0.66	30	-0.16	-0.03	-0.13
4	0.69	0.35	0.34	31	0.21	0.35	-0.14
5	-0.83	-0.41	-0.42	32	0.64	0.62	0.02
6	-0.07	0.17	-0.24	33	0.29	0.35	-0.06
7	-0.16	-0.14	-0.02	34	-0.08	-0.03	-0.05
8	-1.13	-0.60	-0.53	35	-0.29	-0.03	-0.26
9	-0.05	-0.35	0.30	36	0.16	0.35	-0.19
10	0.22	0.16	0.06	37	-0.35	-0.23	-0.12
11	-0.03	0.02	-0.05	38	0.36	0.46	-0.10
12	0.03	0.02	0.01	39	0.05	-0.01	0.06
13	-0.28	-0.35	0.07	40	-0.24	0.14	-0.38
14	1.07	0.40	0.67	41	0.18	0.18	0.00
15	0.42	0.88	-0.46	42	-0.17	-0.01	-0.16
16	-0.16	-0.35	0.19	43	-0.33	0.32	-0.65
17	0.76	0.89	-0.13	44	1.20	0.72	0.48
18	-0.23	-0.56	0.33	45	0.47	0.48	-0.01
19	-0.22	0.02	-0.24	46	0.67	0.86	-0.19
20	0.31	0.61	-0.30	47	0.60	0.72	-0.12
21	-0.14	0.32	-0.46	48	0.80	0.51	0.29
22	0.93	0.38	0.55	49	-0.65	-0.09	-0.56
23	0.25	0.39	-0.14	50	0.08	0.27	-0.19
24	0.36	0.38	-0.02	51	0.54	0.30	0.24
25	0.42	0.38	0.04	52	0.85	0.59	0.26
26	0.91	0.73	0.18	53	0.56	0.52	0.04

Table-4 (contd.)				Table-4 (contd.)			
54	-0.13	0.16	-0.29	101	0.75	0.64	0.11
55	0.22	-0.01	-0.23	102	0.33	0.67	-0.34
56	0.59	0.69	-0.10	103	2.57	2.58	-0.01
57	0.65	0.49	0.16	104	2.18	1.93	0.25
58	0.67	0.60	0.07	105	0.10	0.62	-0.52
59	0.56	0.70	-0.14	106	0.26	1.14	-0.88
60	0.87	0.30	0.57	107	0.75	0.93	-0.18
61	0.42	0.49	-0.07	108	1.65	1.32	0.33
62	0.26	0.49	-0.23	109	1.13	1.32	-0.19
63	0.68	0.93	-0.25	110	1.27	0.96	0.31
64	-0.20	-0.12	-0.08	111	2.72	1.93	0.79
65	-0.03	0.57	-0.60	112	0.43	0.83	-0.40
66	1.04	0.85	0.19	113	0.77	1.01	-0.24
67	0.42	0.01	0.41	114	0.68	0.83	-0.15
68	0.14	0.28	-0.14	115	1.63	1.17	0.46
69	0.58	0.52	0.06	116	2.07	2.48	-0.41
70	1.07	0.91	0.16	117	0.76	0.94	-0.18
71	0.03	0.09	-0.06	118	0.87	1.15	-0.28
72	0.71	0.52	0.19	119	1.66	1.18	0.48
73	1.28	1.03	0.25	120	1.63	1.47	0.16
74	0.53	0.71	-0.18	121	2.66	3.03	-0.37
75	0.72	0.84	-0.12	122	0.80	1.17	-0.37
76	0.76	0.86	-0.10	123	1.30	0.94	0.36
77	1.40	0.81	0.59	124	1.16	1.37	-0.21
78	0.44	0.29	0.15	125	1.13	1.37	-0.24
79	1.56	0.85	0.71	126	1.26	1.18	0.08
80	0.40	0.41	-0.01	127	1.09	0.90	0.19
81	0.87	1.25	-0.38	128	0.99	1.37	-0.38
82	1.30	1.06	0.24	129	1.07	1.37	-0.30
83	1.08	1.25	-0.17	130	1.25	0.94	0.31
84	1.41	1.39	0.02	131	1.41	1.04	0.37
85	0.82	1.03	-0.21	132	1.65	1.65	0.00
86	1.03	0.93	0.10	133	1.81	2.09	-0.28
87	1.78	1.50	0.28	134	1.75	1.51	0.24
88	0.68	1.03	-0.35	135	1.43	1.91	-0.48
89	1.76	1.61	0.15	136	1.53	1.91	-0.38
90	0.45	0.59	-0.14	137	1.51	1.91	-0.40
91	2.10	1.39	0.71	138	0.53	1.08	-0.55
92	2.00	1.80	0.20	139	0.82	1.58	0.76
93	0.37	0.30	0.07	140	2.12	1.51	0.61
94	0.73	0.82	-0.09	141	1.82	2.46	-0.64
95	0.08	0.09	-0.01	142	1.04	1.08	-0.04
96	1.96	1.64	0.32	143	0.72	0.75	-0.03
97	1.91	1.46	0.45	144	1.78	2.46	-0.68
98	1.16	1.14	0.02	145	1.89	1.31	0.58
99	1.09	1.46	-0.37	146	2.21	2.03	0.18
100	0.67	0.42	0.25	147	0.84	0.75	0.09

Table-4 (contd.)

148	1.73	1.29	0.44
149	1.80	2.05	-0.25
150	2.31	1.60	0.71
151	1.06	1.08	-0.02
152	2.42	2.03	0.39
153	1.12	1.30	-0.18
154	1.24	1.41	-0.17
155	1.87	1.65	0.22
156	0.83	1.08	-0.25
157	2.16	1.48	0.68
158	1.71	1.28	0.43
159	2.43	1.99	0.44
160	2.82	3.12	-0.30
161	2.08	1.62	0.46
162	2.60	2.57	0.03
163	2.66	1.80	0.86

One-variable modeling

$$\log \text{IGC}_{50} = -0.019892 + 0.8709454 (\pm 0.05015) F$$

$$N = 166, \text{Se} = 0.4729, R^2 = 0.6520, R^2_A = 0.6498, F = 301.611$$

Two-variable modeling

$$\log \text{IGC}_{50} = -0.0409 + 0.2562 (\pm 0.0280) \pi + 0.7882 (\pm 0.0418) F$$

$$N = 166, \text{Se} = 0.3845, R^2 = 0.7714, R^2_A = 0.7685, F = 269.8812$$

Three-variable modeling

$$\log \text{IGC}_{50} = -0.2868 + 0.0210 (\pm 0.0052) MR + 0.1980 (\pm 0.0303) \pi + 0.6896 (\pm 0.0466) F$$

$$N = 166, \text{Se} = 0.3672, R^2 = 0.8616, R^2_A = 0.8589, F = 336.0343$$

Five-variable modeling

$$\log \text{IGC}_{50} = -0.3758 + 0.0192 (\pm 0.0061) MR + 0.2621 (\pm 0.0318) \pi + 0.8688 (\pm 0.0703) F - 0.2228 (\pm 0.0318) B_1 + 0.1594475 (\pm 0.0318) B_3$$

$$N = 166, \text{Se} = 0.3458, R^2 = 0.8185, R^2_A = 0.8127, F = 141.6428$$

In order to confirm the results obtained using the above model we have calculated the toxicity of 163 compounds using this model and correlated them with the observed toxicities. The results are presented in Fig. 1. The results show that the calculated toxicities are very close to the observed toxicities confirming that the afore mentioned

Fig. 1. Correlation of observed activity with the predicted activity.

model is the most appropriate model for modeling the toxicities of the 163 compounds used.

A close look of therefore mentioned model indicates that coefficients of the parameters π and F are positive indicating that increase in their magnitude increases $\log \text{IGC}_{50}$ while this is not so with the parameter R . The negative coefficient of R indicates that IGC_{50} decreases with decrease in the value of R . This finding will be valuable for medicinal chemists for making new drugs with still better drug activity. This they can do by changing the substitution pattern such that now the substitutions should be such that it results in increasing the value of π and F , at the same time decrease the magnitude of R .

Randic recommendation⁸

Randic^{9,10} stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression, such a descriptor in most studies should be discarded. For example $^1\chi$ and $^2\chi$, $^1\chi$ often strongly correlate and in many structure-property-activity studies $^2\chi$ has been discarded. This is not theoretically justified and despite the widespread practice should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure, it is important to recognize that even highly interrelated descriptors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small but nevertheless very important for structure-property regression.

The criteria for inclusion or exclusion of descriptors should not be based on parallelism between descriptors even if overwhelming, but should be based on whether

the part in which two descriptors disagree is or is not relevant for the characterization of the property considered. If the part in which the second descriptor differ from the first, regardless of how small it is, is relevant for the property under consideration, then the descriptor should be included. Randic further stated that the selection of descriptors to be used in structure-property-activity studies should not be delegated solely to computers, although statistical criteria will continue to be useful for preliminary screening of descriptors taken from a large pool. Often in an automated selection of descriptors, a descriptor will be discarded because it is highly correlated with another descriptor already selected. But what is important is not whether two descriptors parallel one another; i.e. duplicates much of the same structural information, but whether they are complementary in those parts that are important for structure-property-activity correlations. Hence, the residual of the correlation between two descriptors should be examined and kept or discarded depending on how well it can improve the correlation based on already selected descriptors.

Experimental

(i) Calculation of topological indices

All the molecular descriptors are calculated using DRAGON software⁹. The structure optimization was carried out by ACD labs¹⁰ as well as HyperChem¹¹ softwares.

(ii) Model development

Developing statistically most significant model we have used the maximum R² improvement method¹². This method finds the "best" one variable model, the "best" two variable model and so for the prediction of log IGC₅₀. In doing so correlation analysis using the method of least square method is adopted where is log IGC₅₀ is correlated in each of the topological indices along with their variety of combinations.

(iii) Presentation of the data

Table 1 gives the structural details of the compounds used. The log (IGC₅₀⁻¹) and the values of sterimol as well as structural parameters are recorded in Table 2. The regressive parameters and quality of correlations for the possible models obtained using NCSS software¹² are given in Table 3. The details most appropriate model are given in Table 4. The correlation of the estimated activities with the observed one are demonstrated in Fig. 1 shown in Figs 1. and 2 for 7-parametric and 8-parametric models.

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